

Global 30 m Digital Terrain Model (DTM)

Is It Time to Ditch Copernicus DEM for Wind & Renewables?

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NASA image of Endeavour taking off on its STS-99 mission

1. Introduction

- Motivation for this presentation and analysis
- What model? DEM, DTM, DSM?
- Overview of global DEM's

2. Digital Elevation Models (DEM)

- What are we using before and now
- Expected accuracy from models
- Overview of GEDTM30 – and known issues

3. Analysis – Value of Elevation Models

- Metrics considered and used
- Analysis: At turbine and random locations
- Analysis: In forest or at water-body

4. Lessons Learned

- Is It Time to Ditch Copernicus DEM for Wind & Renewables?

What motivates this presentation and study?

Image Credit: JAXA

1. Release of the GEDTM30 DTM

- Have been waiting for an open source DTM
- First (to my knowledge) fully open-data global Digital Terrain Model dataset was released on May 22nd 2025.
- It one of a number of DTM's (with commercial or less permissive licenses) that utilized the amazing Copernicus DEM/DSM and other geo-datasets to create a DTM

2. Recommendation - which 'default' DEM to use now

- a lot of new high quality sources to choose from
- what is the best 'default' choice for DEM for wind farms
- goal is to have something that is 'good enough' and analysis ready and decide for which use-cases is it suitable

3. Analysis to identify any known or unknown pitfalls

- analyze DEM-quality at wind turbine sites and random locations
- outline any known pitfalls
- independent analysis focused on wind-turbine locations

Digital Elevation Models (DEM)

What type of elevation model? DEM, DSM, DTM?

DEM: Digital Elevation Model

Is often used as a generic term for both DSM's & DTM's

DSM: Digital Surface Model

Surface representation with objects

DTM: Digital Terrain Model

Bare earth representation without objects

Overview of Major (Near) Global DEM and DSM's

From where does this awesome data actually originate?

SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission)

- **Technology:** Radar (C-band)
- **Year:** 2000
- **Agency:** NASA
- **Dataset(s)**
 - SRTM3 (90m)
 - SRTM1 (30m)
 - NASADEM
- **Coverage:** 60N-56S
- **License:** Open / public domain

TanDEM-X

- **Technology:** Radar (X-band)
- **Years:** 2010-2026
- **Agency:** DLR and Airbus
- **Dataset(s)**
 - TandemX (12m)
 - CopernicusDEM (10m, 30m, 90m)
- **Coverage:** Global
- **Licenses:**
 - TandemX: 12m-commercial, 90m restricted
 - CopDEM: 10m: Restricted, 30m, 90m: Open

ALOS World 3D (AW3D30)

- **Technology:** Optical stereo
- **Years:** 2006-2011
- **Agency:** JAXA (Japan)
- **Dataset:** AW3D30
- **Coverage:** Global
- **Licenses:**
 - 2.5m and 5m: Commercial via NTT data
 - 30m: Open

ASTER GDEM

- **Technology:** Optical stereo (ASTER instrument on Terra satellite)
- **Years:** 1999-present (still operational)
- **Agency:** NASA (USA) and METI (Japan)
- **Dataset:** ASTER GDEM v3 (2019)
- **Coverage:** 83N - 83S
- **Licenses:** Open / public domain

What are we using now (and then)?

Statistics from windPRO user usage

Download of Digital Elevation Data in windPRO - August 2018

Download of DEM data in windPRO - August 2025

Evaluating Accuracy and Vertical Error

What is the 'standard' accuracy – and what metrics to use?

Global Datasources	Grid [m]	Vertical Accuracy		Vertical Datum	Technology
ALOS-AW3D30	30.0	7.0	LE90	-	Satellite - optical - stereo imagery
ASTER GDEM v2	30.0	15.0 - 20.0	LE90	-	Optical - stereo imagery
Copernicus DEM - 10m	30.0	2.2	LE90	EGM2008	Radar
SRTM1	30.0	6.0 - 9.0	LE90	EGM96	C-Band radar (~ 5cm)
SRTM3	90.0	< 16.0	-	EGM96	C-Band radar (~ 5cm)
Regional Datasources	Grid [m]	Vertical Accuracy		Vertical Datum	Technology
ArcticDEM	2.0			-	
EU-DEM	30.0	2.9	RMS	-	Multi-source: SRTM and contour lines
ViewFinder	90.0	-	-	-	Multi-source: SRTM and contour lines
National Datasources	Grid [m]	Vertical Accuracy		Vertical Datum	Technology
Belgium-Flandern	5.0	0.05	-	TAW	LiDAR
Danish Elevation Model	0.4	0.05	-	DVR90	LiDAR
Finish Elevation Model	10.0	1.4	P95	N2000	Mix: Contours, stereo-imagery and LiDAR
German NRW Model	1.0	0.20	-	-	LiDAR
Netherlands - AHN2	0.5	0.20	P99.7	-	LiDAR
Slovenia Elevation Model	1.0	< 0.11	RMS	-	LiDAR
Swedish GSD50+ NH	50.0	1.00	P50	-	LiDAR
UK-Northern Ireland	10.0	1.00	RMSE	Belfast Lough	Stereo Imagery
US NED	10.0	3.04	P95	-	-
Commercial Datasources	Grid [m]	Vertical Accuracy		Vertical Datum	Technology
ALOS-AW3D30	5.0	4.1	RMSE	-	Satellite - optical - stereo imagery
Euro Maps 3D	5.0	5.0 - 10.0	LE90	EGM96	Optical - stereo imagery - Cartosat-1
WorldDEM	12.0	< 4.0	LE90	-	X-Band radar (~ 3 cm)
Vricon DSM-0.5	0.5	3.0	LE90	-	Satellite - optical - Digital Globe
Vricon DSM-10	10.0	3.0	LE90	-	Satellite - optical - Digital Globe
NEXTMap-10	10.0	10.0	LE95	-	?
NEXTMap One	1.0	3.6	LE95	-	2016 or newer satellite data

GEDTM30

Global Ensemble Digital Terrain Model at 30 m resolution.

License and Release Date

It is a fully open, global, gap-free digital terrain model (DTM) at ~30 m spatial resolution, released in 2025. (CC-BY-40)

Model Technique

Elevation Data: The model is produced by fusing multiple high-quality global datasets (notably Copernicus DEM and ALOS AW3D30).

ML- Usage: Random Forests trained on billions of globally distributed spaceborne LiDAR points (ICESat-2 and GEDI) to remove above-ground objects (vegetation, buildings) and estimate the “bare earth” elevation.

Validation:

Against LiDAR DTM’s and GNSS station data.
Reduces RMSE with 25-30% in build-up and forested-areas.

Main Author: Yu-Feng Ho (OpenGeoHub, Netherlands)

Any known issues with the data?

Lower Accuracy

- Coastal-zones

Higher uncertainty

- In dense forests
- At steep slopes

Artifacts

- At water bodies, where DEM's disagree

Terrain Representation

- 2006-2015 (because of input-data)

Image: AW3D30, SRTM, CopernicusDEM and GEDTM30 in windPRO at Lake Muritz, Germany.

Typically, national or regional DEM's have better accuracy than global ones – but is is also very technology dependent – with LiDAR campaigns in cm-range

Evaluating Accuracy and Vertical Error

What is the 'standard' accuracy – and what metrics to use?

Vertical error for datasets is determined from ground control points (GCP's) – at Turbine Locations & Random.

Vertical error:

$$\Delta Z = Z_{\text{DEM}} - Z_{\text{REF}}$$

Metrics / statistics:

- Mean error (bias)
- Standard deviation
- Root mean square error (RMSE)
- Quantiles (P25, P50; P75, P90, P95 & P99)

GCP's may come from

- LiDAR campaigns
- Airport runways
- IceSAT2 / GEDI data (satellite LiDAR's)
- High-quality national datasets

Accuracy also depends on:

- Location, slope, land-cover, vegetation, height...
- Technology use in obtaining the dataset

Increasing accuracy / precision / resolution

GLOBAL DATA

REGIONAL DATA

NATIONAL DATA

LOCAL/SITE DATA

George E.P. Box

Box-and-Whiskers: Setup with percentiles 10, 25, 50, 75 and 90.

Box-and-Whiskers: Setup with percentiles 10, 25, 50, 75 and 90.

Box-and-Whiskers: Setup with percentiles 10, 25, 50, 75 and 90.

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Is It Time to Ditch Copernicus DEM for Wind & Renewables?

No – but time to ditch other models that these:

- Use a national model, if possible
- CopernicusDEM 30m is a good default choice – much better than SRTM
- GEDTM30 would be the default choice, if in forests or in need of a DTM (but inspect near water-bodies)

Image-Top: The two radar satellites TanDEM-X and TerraSAR-X in close formation flight at a distance of 350m apart. Credit DLR (CC-BY-3.0)

Image-Bottom: WorldView Satellite in Stereoscopic Mode. Credit: PGC & Digital Globe.

Thank you!

↓ Think energy differently

17/11/2025

Global 30 m Digital Terrain Model (DTM)

RECAST: Data used in this project were developed as a part of the RECAST project. RECAST is a joint R&D project with participants from the wind energy industry and academia: EMD, Vestas, RES and DTU. The RECAST project is co-funded by the Innovation Fund Denmark.

GASP: GASP 1.0, by EMD and DTU, is a free dataset accessible via windprospecting.com, windPRO and EMD-API.

InnoWind: InnoWind was a joint R&D effort for improving land-surface models for wind energy modelling. The project focused on land-surface modelling with the aid of modern satellite sensors and remote sensing equipment. The project was executed during years 2017-2020 as a co-operation between EMD, DTU DHI-GRAS, Vestas and Vattenfall and co-funding from the Innovation Fund Denmark.

CopernicusDEM: Copernicus DEM GLO-90 (Copernicus WorldDEM™-90) or Copernicus DEM GLO-30 (Copernicus WorldDEM™-30) -unmodified data: - © DLR e.V. 2010-2014 and © Airbus Defence and Space GmbH 2014-2018 provided under COPERNICUS by the European Union and ESA; all rights reserved. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/emd-copernicusdem>

Global Elevation Data Testing Facility (GEDTF): Kazimierz Bęcek, Monika Stepnowska, Jakub Łuczak. Global Elevation Data Testing Facility (GEDTF). [dataset, database] Available in Atlas of Open Science Resources, <https://www.zasobynauki.pl/zasoby/global-elevation-data-testing-facility-gedtf,49859/>. License: CC BY-SA 4.0, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/legalcode.pl>. Date of access: 20.09.2021.

NASADEM: Contains NASADEM elevation data. Courtesy NASA/JPL-Caltech. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/emd-nasadem>

SRTM: NASA, team around STS-99 and the US public are thanked for making this great digital elevation dataset available in the public domain and thus for aiding the development of renewable energy. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/emd-srtm>

AW3D30: Contains AW3D30 elevation data from the JAXA - Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (@JAXA). Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/emd-aw3d30>

Germany Berlin DGM: Based on data from Geoportal Berlin / ATKIS® DGM1 / Datenlizenz Deutschland – Namensnennung – Version 2.0. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/emd-berlindgm>

Germany Brandenburg DGM: Based on data from Geobroker Brandenburg / © GeoBasis-DE/LGB, dl-de/by-2-0, 2020 Datenlizenz Deutschland - Namensnennung - Version 2.0. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/emd-brandenburgdgm>

German Hamburg DGM: Based on data from Freie und Hansestadt Hamburg, Landesbetrieb Geoinformation und Vermessung (LGV), DGM1. Datenlizenz Deutschland – Namensnennung – Version 2.0. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/dgm-hamburg>

German Nordrhein-Westfalen DGM: Contains modified elevation data from Geobasis NRW (geobasis.nrw.de). dl-de/by-2-0. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/dgm-de-nrw>

Germany Saxony DGM:

Based on elevation data from GeoSN, Data license Germany – attribution – version 2.0. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/dgm-saxony>

Germany Saxony-Anhalt DGM: Elevation model based on data from © GeoBasis-DE / LVermGeo LSA. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/dgm-saxonyanhalt>

Germany Thuringia DGM: Elevation model based on data from © GDI-Th / Datenlizenz Deutschland – Namensnennung – Version 2.0. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/dgm-thuringia>

Acknowledgements

UK Scotland DTM: Contains public sector information licensed under the Open Government Licence v3.0: <http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/>. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/dtm-scotland>

UK Wales DTM: Contains Natural Resources Wales Information ©. Natural Resources Wales and database right. CC-BY-4.0. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/dtm-wales>

Spain MNT: Elevation data from the Spanish Instituto Geográfico Nacional (IGN). MNT05/MTD25 2008-2019 CC-BY 4.0 ign.es. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/emd-spainmnt>

Belgium-Flemish DTM: Contains elevation data from the Agency of Geographical Information Flanders (Agentschap voor Geografische Informatie Vlaanderen). Digital Height Model Flanders 2013-2015. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/belgium-flemish>

Belgium-Walloon MNT: Based on data from "Service public de Wallonie (SPW)" - <http://geoportail.wallonie.be>. Modèle Numérique de Terrain (MNT) 2013-2014. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/emd-belgium-walloon>

France MNT: Contains elevation data from the Institut National de l'Information Géographique et Forestière (IGN) – 05/2019 & 03/2021. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/emd-francemnt>

Estonia DTM: Elevation data: Estonian Land Board 2012-2017. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/dtm-estonia>

Slovenia DTM: Modified elevation data from Agencija RS za okolje. Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/dtm-slovenia>

Netherlands AHN: Data from the Actueel Hoogtebestand Nederland (AHN). Read more: <https://tinyurl.com/ahn-netherlands>

GEDTM30: Ho, Y.-F., Grohmann, C.H., Lindsay, J., Reuter, H.I., Parente, L., Witjes, M., & Hengl, T. (2025). Global Ensemble Digital Terrain modeling and parametrization at 30 m resolution (GEDTM30): a data fusion approach based on ICESat-2, GEDI and multisource data. [Preprint]. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-6280607/v1>

Luxembourg MNT: Data from the administration of cadastre and topography in Luxembourg (ACT). More: <https://tinyurl.com/mnt-luxembourg>

MERITDEM: MERIT DEM: Multi-Error-Removed Improved-Terrain DEM. CC-BY-40-NC.

FABDEM: FABDEM (Forest And Buildings removed Copernicus DEM) is a global elevation map that removes building and tree height biases from the Copernicus GLO 30 Digital Elevation Model (DEM). The data is available at 1 arc second grid spacing (approximately 30m at the equator) for the globe. CC-BY-40-NC.